

Data-driven Residential Flexibility for Student Housing

ABSTRACT

The Romanian pilot of DEDALUS shows how **data-driven residential flexibility** can be tested in a student housing environment. Implemented across university dormitory buildings, the pilot combines structured data modelling, predictive digital twin services and a blockchain-enabled flexibility market. It also highlights the value of **hands-on engagement and educational support** when advanced digital tools are introduced to residential users.

KEY POINTS

- Validating data-driven flexibility in a dynamic, real-life student dormitory environment characterised by highly variable occupancy.
- Combining privacy-preserving blockchain markets with advanced multi-token standards to successfully automate local energy trading and secure settlements.
- Deploying an interoperable digital twin to seamlessly disaggregate building-level data and optimise apartment-level flexibility without requiring intrusive metering hardware.
- Useful lessons for introducing complex decentralised technologies to residential energy communities.

The Romanian pilot is implemented in a **university residence context** and focuses on residential flexibility in student dormitories. The pilot infrastructure covers two dormitory buildings with **468 rooms** and relies on energy consumption measurements collected through the local building management system. This makes it a relevant setting for testing advanced, data-driven DR services that must overcome the lack of granular, apartment-level monitoring infrastructure.

INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGIES AND SERVICES

The Romanian pilot combines interoperable tools supporting monitoring, forecasting and transactional flexibility services:

- **DEDALUS ontology-compliant data model**, extended in the large-scale cycle to include pilot-specific user preferences alongside rooms, sensors and devices.
- **Blockchain and smart contracts market**, enhanced with the ERC-1155 multi-token standard (to reduce transaction costs and handle multiple token types simultaneously) and homomorphic encryption (HE) to execute privacy-preserving, on-chain P2P market matching, commitments and settlements.
- **Apartment Building Digital Twin**, developed to compensate for the lack of apartment-level monitoring by modelling apartments, performing load disaggregation and selecting the minimum number of apartments to involve in DR actions.
- **Dashboards and visualisation tools**, supporting users and managers to seamlessly use their locally stored private keys to decrypt and view their trading sessions, commitments and financial settlements.

ENGAGEMENT

- Successfully engaged **152 consumers** (primarily university students and staff) in residential DR.
- The Romanian pilot implemented **5 engagement activities**. Main formats included a co-creation workshop, technical workshop, dashboard-based interaction, smart contract-related activities and a post-test questionnaire.
- Capitalised on the academic setting by executing physical, **hands-on technical workshops** that provided dedicated learning materials, proving far more effective for gathering experience-based feedback than explanation-only formats.
- At the same time, the pilot shows that advanced technologies such as blockchain require clear introductory explanations and **structured user familiarisation**.

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● KEY RESULTS

- The Romanian pilot recorded a **21.3% energy efficiency increase** through predictive digital twin services, successfully overcoming the severe data complexities caused by students' academic vacations.
- It mobilised **13.81% of aggregated flexibility** through a simulated blockchain-driven peer-to-peer flexibility market.
- It achieved a **24% carbon emissions reduction** linked to the local energy grid by accurately predicting day-ahead consumption and optimising DR offers.

● REPLICATION RELEVANCE

- **Residential DR services** can benefit from combining **interoperable data models**, **predictive digital twin services** and **privacy-preserving blockchain mechanisms** within one integrated system.
- **Student housing environments** can provide a strong testbed for advanced flexibility services, especially in campus-like or high-density residential settings.
- Future replication can preserve the **core service logic** while adapting the data integration layer to local APIs, consumption patterns and infrastructure constraints.
- The replication of the Romanian blockchain solution in Spain confirms the **transferability of the approach** beyond the original pilot context

● RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Educational support** should be treated as a core condition when users are asked to interact with **complex digital services**.
- **Structured user familiarisation** should accompany the introduction of advanced technologies such as blockchain.
- **Well-documented APIs** and reliable data flows should be prioritised to support effective deployment and future replication.
- Technical innovation should be matched with **engagement formats** that enable users to understand, test and provide feedback on the services.

REFERENCES

D5.4: DEDALUS impact and social acceptance analysis, 2026.